

Enhancing the Quality and Recognition of Local Journals: Recommendations to ZIMCHE

IMPRESSUM

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Foreword

Local journals in developing countries play a pivotal role in leveraging science and technology for economic, social, and environmental development, as they provide a platform for disseminating locally relevant research, fostering innovation, and informing policy-making in alignment with the unique needs and contexts of these countries.

The Zimbabwe Young Academy of Sciences (ZimYAS) is an independent platform of outstanding scholars with research and innovation development expertise. We are actively involved in advancing science, technology and innovation in Zimbabwe, South Africa, China, Namibia, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America. Our members are involved in the various stages of the editorial process of academic publishing in reputable international journals:

Peer review: engaged in assessment and evaluation of research published in top journals.

Editorial board: sit on editorial boards where they evaluate manuscripts for novelty.

Journal editor: make decisions about manuscripts and shape the journal's vision.

Researchers: involved in conducting world-class research which they submit to journals.

Introduction

This policy memo proposes a strategic framework for the Zimbabwe Council for Higher Education (ZIMCHE) to consider in creating the proposed accredited journal list. The focus is on including local journals, which lack the necessary infrastructure for wider dissemination and recognition. Drawing on international best practices, the policy memo offers a comprehensive process to enhance the quality and visibility of these journals, ensuring they meet the standards for accreditation and contribute significantly to Zimbabwe's academic landscape.

As the Zimbabwe Young Academy of Sciences identified, we identified guidelines for including local journals in the proposed ZIMCHE accredited list.

Develop a transparent submission and evaluation procedure with clear requirements and expectations on inclusion.

Assemble a competent and diverse journal evaluation panel with a rich background in research and publishing at international level.

Evaluate the journal's content quality, relevance to the Zimbabwean research community, and compliance with international standards.

Provide support for international indexing. Conduct regular reviews and monitoring of the journal's editorial quality and publishing consistency.

The third and fourth steps will ensure the journals are regionally competitive, which is essential for Zimbabwe to meet Vision 2030: Zimbabwe must transition from being mere consumers of international research to becoming producers of globally recognized scholarly work, facilitated by the elevation of our local journals.

R&D transformation is only possible if we have the infrastructure for disseminating of novel ideas, processes, and products.

Background

The prevalence of publishing in predatory journals among Zimbabwean academics is a growing concern. This practice, driven either by a lack of knowledge or academic fraud, has seen some individuals promoted to a professorship with several publications in questionable journals. Such practices tarnish the image of Zimbabwean universities and the country at large.

ZIMCHE has a crucial role to play in curbing these practices. One of the most effective approaches is the proposed accredited journal list. While selecting international journals for inclusion is relatively straightforward, as the list can be obtained from recognized databases such as SCOPUS and Web of Knowledge, including local journals is complex. Local journals are not indexed on reputable international databases such as SCOPUS and Web of Knowledge. Only a few are indexed on Africa Journal Online, most of which are no longer operational. Additionally, local journals are fragmented; no central system monitors their quality, progress, and reach.

Local journals play a vital role in disseminating research that addresses the local needs of developing countries, which is unlikely to attract much attention from the global academic community (Tijssen et al., 2006). Tijssen et al. (2006) noted that local journals are the best ‘vehicles for disseminating relevant results of indigenous research activities dealing with issues or problems of predominantly or exclusively local relevance’.

The Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) in South Africa has used accredited journal lists to rehabilitate local journals and incentivize academics to publish quality research. Guidelines must be set for local journals to be included in the ZIMCHE-accredited journal list. Setting up these guidelines at international standards will facilitate the journals to be eligible for indexing in international databases such as SCOPUS, Web of Knowledge, and Directory of Open Access Journals.

Review of International Best Practices

SCOPUS Guidelines

SCOPUS, a bibliographic database containing abstracts and citations for academic journal articles, has set forth a comprehensive set of guidelines for journal evaluation. It is a comprehensive abstract and citation database of peer-reviewed literature, including scientific journals, books, and conference proceedings. It provides a comprehensive overview of the world's science, technology, medicine, social sciences, arts, and humanities research output. Scopus features smart tools to track, analyze and visualize research.

Scopus currently includes over 90 million records and has established relationships with 7,000 publishers in 105 countries. This allows it to provide content from 27,950 active peer-reviewed journals. It also includes a significant amount of Open Access content, with 20.54 million open-access articles and 6,126 open-access journals.

Scopus has a rigorous content selection process managed by an independent Content Selection & Advisory Board (CSAB) to ensure that only high-quality and relevant titles are included. The CSAB uses a set of quantitative and qualitative measures to evaluate each title, including:

- **Journal Policy:** The journal should have a clear peer-review process and ethical guidelines for authors and reviewers.
- **Content:** The journal should publish original content in the English language.
- **Journal Standing:** a reputable editorial board, be recognized by the academic community, and a convincing publishing history.
- **Regularity:** The journal should adhere to its stated publication schedule.
- **Online Availability:** The journal should have a website with an ISSN and contact details.

Journal Policy

- Convincing editorial policy
- Type of peer review
- Diversity in geographical distribution of editors
- Diversity in geographical distribution of authors

Content

- Academic contribution to the field
- Clarity of abstracts
- Quality of and conformity to the stated aims and scope of the journal
- Readability of articles

Journal Standing

- Citedness of journal articles in Scopus
- Editor standing

Publishing Regularity

- No delays or interruptions in the publication schedule

Online Availability

- Full journal content available online
- English language journal home page available
- Quality of journal home page

Scopus has a rigorous content selection process managed by an independent Content Selection & Advisory Board (CSAB) to ensure that only high-quality and relevant titles are included.

Review of International Best Practices Continued

Clarivate Guidelines

Clarivate Analytics, the company behind the Web of Science (WoS), also has a stringent process for selecting journals for inclusion in its database. The WoS Core Collection is a curated set of over 21,000 peer-reviewed, high-quality scholarly journals published worldwide in over 250 science, social sciences, and humanities disciplines.

The selection process for WoS involves several stages. After an initial triage for gathering general information about the journal, it is submitted to an editorial triage, where a set of 28 criteria is applied. These include 24 quality criteria and four criteria of impact. The main criteria are that the source must be peer-reviewed, published on time, comply with editorial standards, and meet certain citation thresholds indicating its impact. Additionally, the linguistic criterion requires abstracts and titles to be written in English, and the content must have international relevance.

Review of National and Regional Best Practices Continued

South Africa

In South Africa, the Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) has established a successful model for accrediting academic journals. The DHET's Procedure for the Accreditation of Journals outlines the eligibility criteria and application process for inclusion in the accredited list. Key eligibility criteria include evidence of peer review, regularity of publication, diversity of authors, and an editorial board comprising experts in the relevant field. The journal's international standing, as evidenced by its inclusion in international databases and citation indexes, is also considered. The DHET's approach has incentivized academics to publish quality research, thereby enhancing the international reputation of South African research

Pakistan

Pakistan's Higher Education Commission (HEC) has developed an IT-based accreditation and ranking system tailored to its needs and requirements. The HEC's Journal Recognition System outlines the eligibility criteria for journal accreditation. These include having clearly defined aims, objectives, and scope of publication, an ISSN number, a registered title, and a functional URL. The journal must also be owned and published by a registered entity. The HEC categorizes journals into Y, X, or W categories, with W being the highest category. The categorization is based on the journal's fulfilment of quality criteria, international recognition, and citation information.

African Journals Online

African Journals Online (AJOL) is a web platform dedicated to increasing the international profile of Africa's scholarly work and improving access to African-originated knowledge. It hosts 524 journals, providing them with international exposure to over 100,000 researchers each month. AJOL offers a range of services to its partner journals, including a free journal home page, free metadata hosting, free full-text hosting, and a potential extra revenue stream from article downloads.

It also provides guidelines for journals to meet various criteria for inclusion, such as scholarly content, peer review and quality control, a functional Editorial Board, a registered ISSN and eISSN, and a commitment to upload all content for inclusion on AJOL. By adhering to these guidelines and standards, local journals can increase their visibility and accessibility, reaching a wider audience and contributing to the global knowledge base.

AJOL listing criteria

- The journal must be scholarly in content, actively publishing, and contain original research articles.
- The journal's content must be peer-reviewed and quality controlled.
- The journal must have a functional Editorial Board, with all people listed actively involved and up to date.
- The journal must have a registered ISSN and eISSN.
- The journal agrees to upload or provide all content for inclusion on AJOL.
- The journal guarantees all requisite permissions are granted to allow AJOL to operate an article download service.
- The journal must be published by a stipulated publishing entity that is based in the African continent.

AJOL ensures that African journals meet international standards, enhancing their visibility and impact.

Recommendations: What should ZIMCHE do?

Recommendations for Guidelines to Include Local Journals in the Proposed ZIMCHE Accredited List	
Submission Process	ZIMCHE should create a detailed online submission form that local journals must complete to apply for accreditation. It should include information on the journal's peer review process, publication regularity, authors' diversity, the editorial board's composition, journal homepage, and ISSN. It should also require evidence of peer review guidelines, publication schedules, a list of past authors and their affiliations, and bios of editorial board members.
Selection of Assessment Panel	ZIMCHE should establish an independent assessment panel comprising individuals with experience in peer review, hold editorial roles in internationally or regionally indexed or accredited journals, and have an extensive publishing record. The selection process for the panel should be based on a clear set of criteria, including academic qualifications, publishing record, and experience in journal editing and peer review.
Journal rankings	ZIMCHE should adopt a ranking system for local journals similar to the one used by Pakistan's Higher Education Commission. This system should categorize journals into different tiers based on their fulfillment of quality criteria, international recognition, and citation information. The exact criteria for each tier should be clearly defined and made publicly available.

Recommendations for Guidelines to Include Local Journals in the Proposed ZIMCHE Accredited List

Assistance with International Indexing	ZIMCHE should establish a program to assist local journals in getting indexed by international databases such as Clarivate, SCOPUS, and African Journals Online. This program could include workshops and training sessions on meeting the indexing criteria of these databases, one-on-one consultations with journal editors, and assistance with the application process for indexing.
Regular Review and Monitoring	Once a journal is included in the ZIMCHE accredited list, it should be subject to regular reviews, at least biennially, to ensure that it continues to meet the accreditation criteria. The review process should involve a reassessment of the journal's compliance with the standards used in the initial accreditation process, as well as an evaluation of any changes in the journal's operations or quality. The results of these reviews should be made publicly available to ensure transparency and accountability.

Guidelines must be set for local journals to be included in the ZIMCHE-accredited journal list. Setting up these guidelines at international standards will facilitate the journals to be eligible for indexing in international databases.

Initial assessment

Conclusion

Establishing an accredited journal list by the ZIMCHE presents a significant opportunity to enhance local journals' quality and international recognition in Zimbabwe. By adopting a robust and transparent accreditation process, informed by global and regional best practices, ZIMCHE can ensure that local journals meet high standards of quality, relevance, and integrity.

The proposed recommendations provide a comprehensive and actionable framework for accrediting local journals. They emphasize the importance of a clear submission process, a competent and diverse assessment panel, thorough editorial assessment, a fair and transparent ranking system, assistance for international indexing, and regular review and monitoring.

Implementing these recommendations will improve the quality of local journals and promote quality research in Zimbabwe. This, in turn, will contribute to the country's academic reputation and the advancement of knowledge in various fields.

Next Steps

ZIMYAS is committed to disseminating these recommendations to the target stakeholders, drawing on the young academy's expertise and those of the parent organization, the Zimbabwe Academy of Sciences.

It is anticipated that this policy brief and the corresponding research publications by ZIMYAS members will inform policymakers at the institutional, city, provincial, sectoral, and national levels. Evidence-based policymaking is imperative for Zimbabwe to meet the SDGs and Vision 2030.

ZIMYAS is open to partnerships with institutions and government departments interested in implementing the recommendations laid out in this policy brief. The partners will benefit from the knowledge and global experience of our members, who are outstanding researchers. Opportunities for working with the African Union and UNESCO will be pursued within the context of leveraging science, technology and innovation for social, economic, and environmental development.

Stakeholders interested in any aspects of this policy brief, particularly the implementation of the recommendations, must contact ZIMYAS at edmond@zimbabweyas.org or check our website <https://www.zimbabweyas.org>.

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He is an assistant professor in the Department of Applied Sciences at Northumbria University, United Kingdom. Before that, he was an associate professor at the Institute of Marine Science at Shantou University, China. He obtained his PhD at the University of California Riverside, USA and his BSc (Hons) at the National University of Science and Technology, Zimbabwe. He has written more than 50 research papers in reputable international peer review journals and sits on the editorial board of several journals, including Communications Earth & Environment and BMC Chemistry. He is a member of the Global Young Academy and a Fellow of the Institution of Environmental Science. More about his research and publications can be found here:

<https://www.northumbria.ac.uk/about-us/our-staff/s/edmond-sanganyado/>

Zimbabwe Young Academy of Sciences promotes research excellence and cross-disciplinary collaboration between outstanding young scholars.

Zimbabwe Young Academy of Sciences is an independent, cross-disciplinary platform for outstanding young scholars in Zimbabwe and the Diaspora that seek to foster research excellence through scientific capacity building, promotion of interdisciplinary collaborations, and contributions to societal development.

